

A Sogdian Zoroastrian Prayer

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Entry tags: Text, Zoroastrian prayer, Zoroastrianism, Religious Group

c. 9th c. CE The manuscript containing this text was among the 14,000 or so documents from the Library Cave (Cave 17) at Dunhuang, which were brought to Britain in by Aurel Stein in the early 20th century. The two lines of the text containing the Ashem Vohu prayer were not deciphered until the mid-1970s (See bibliography attached to this entry). This discovery represents the oldest written text, in Old Iranian, of a prayer that is regularly recited by Zoroastrians today. The Zoroastrian religion traces its roots to the pronouncements of an ancient Iranian named Zarathustra, which were transmitted in a language now known as "Avestan." As the Iranians moved across the eastern Eurasian steppes towards the plateau of Iran, several groups remained in what is now Central Asia. The Sogdians, who spoke an eastern (middle) Iranian language seem to have retained aspects of the religion that differed in expression from the Sasanian Zoroastrians. The identification of the Ashem Vohu prayer, which varies from the form of the prayer as preserved in the Sasanian Avesta, indicates that it was central to the religion from a very early period.

Date Range: 400 CE - 900 CE

Region: Mogao Caves, Dunhuang and Sogdiana

Region tags: China, Gansu

Dunhuang, Gansu Province, North Central China
Sogdiana: modern Uzenkistan, Tajikistan Although not labelled, the Mogao caves at Dunhuang are located in the northwest of Gansu (see marker)

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sims-Williams, Nicholas (2000). Some Reflections on Zoroastrianism in Sogdiana and Bactria. In *Realms of the Silk Roads: Ancient and Modern*, eds. David Christian and Craig Benjamin; 1-12. Turnhout: Brepols
- Source 1: Gershevitch, Ilya (1976) 'The Sogdian Fragments of the British Library: Appendix.' *Indo-Iranian Journal* 18 (1-2): 75-82.
- Source 2: Sims-Williams, Nicholas (1976) 'The Sogdian Fragments of the British Library.' *Indo-Iranian Journal* 18 (1-2): 43-82
- Source 3: Grenet, Frantz and Guangda, Zhang (1996). 'The Last Refuge of the Sogdian Religion: Dunhuang in the Ninth and Tenth Centuries.' *Bulletin of the Asia Institute New Series*, Vol. 10, Studies in Honor of Vladimir A. Livshits; pp 175-186

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bl.uk/collection-items/zoroastrian-prayer>
- Source 1 Description: The British Library website, providing a brief contextualization of the manuscript and the prayer.
- Source 2 URL: <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/asem-vohu-the-second-of-the-four-great-prayers>
- Source 2 Description: Article in the Encyclopaedia Iranica on the Ashem Vohu prayer

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://titus.uni-frankfurt.de/texte/etcs/iran/miran/sogd/sogdnswc/sogdn.htm?sogdn214.htm>
- Source 1 Description: This source currently includes Manichaean and Buddhist texts in the British Library collection. It will at some point incorporate the Sogdian "Zoroastrian" texts, the Rustom fragment and the Ancient Letters
- Source 1 URL: http://www.avesta.org/kanga/ka_english_kanga_epub.pdf
- Source 1 Description: This is a subsection of the www.avesta.org website, a collection of primary sources relating to the Zoroastrian religion. This links directly to an English translation of the Khordeh Avesta, a collection of prayers, of which the Ashem Vohu is the first
- Source 1 URL: http://idp.bl.uk/database/search_results.a4d?uid=1453691195;random=28465
- Source 1 Description: This database, part of the International Dunhuang Project, links to the European collections of materials found at the Mogao caves, and elsewhere along the 'Silk Roads.' Information about Sogdiana can be found in various sections of the website

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

- ↳ Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: Studies of some of the paper manuscripts in the Stein collection show that much of it

was rag paper with a plant base. The specific paper for the Sogdian MS has not been tested.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Although some of the papers in the Library Cave seem to have been written/overwritten, the Sogdian manuscript appears to be on clean paper

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The text seems to have been passed down orally. It differs significantly from the Avestan form of the prayer as now known.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was discovered alongside nearly 50,000 ancient manuscripts, silk paintings and embroideries, and other textiles dating between the 5th and early 11th centuries. At that point, the cave and its contents were sealed for reasons that remain unclear.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: There were silk paintings and ink on paper drawings stored in the Library Cave. The open Mogao caves contained mostly Buddhist images and murals. See the note below regarding locations of imagery in Sogdian Zoroastrian contexts in Sogdiana and in Chang'An/Xi'an, and elsewhere in China.

Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

- At home
- Religious space with restricted access
- Some public spaces

Notes: One Chinese account alludes to a Zoroastrian (Ch. xian) temple to the east of Dunhuang, which had painted deities in twenty niches (See Grenet & Guangda, "The Last Refuge," p. 175). In Sogdiana, murals on the walls of 6th-8th century palaces and temples illustrate some of the local religious practices, as does the iconography on ossuaries, used to hold the dry bones of the deceased after exposure. Recent discoveries of 6th-century Sogdian funerary artifacts around Xi'an display similar iconography, as well as scenes from the daily life of Sogdian officials in China.

Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: Some Sogdian ossuaries contain imagery of Zoroastrian yazatas, and a few depict the journey of the soul of the deceased to the afterlife. The figure of one or two priests who seem to be conducting the fourth-day ritual after death appear on both ossuaries and the funerary monuments found in Xi'an. A riderless horse, thought to depict Mithra, is found on an ossuary and a mural at Afrasiyab. Other murals from Sogdiana illustrate a rich repertoire of divinities.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Notes: See note above regarding the riderless horse. The priests on some of the Sogdian funerary monuments from China are portrayed with bird legs, tail and wings (cf. the figures on either side of the solar charioteer fresco at Bamiyan). This is thought to depict the association of the priestly activity relating to death rituals with the role of the rooster, which, in the Videvdad is described as "assistant to Sraosha" (Vd. 18.14–16). Sraosha is the yazata that protects the soul for the three days after death and then accompanies it to the place of reckoning and then across the bridge (Y 57.25; Menog-i Xrad 1.115-123)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: See above response regarding the "bird-priest" iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– Yes

Notes: The fire - as the focus of reverence in Sogdian murals, funerary iconography, and graffiti on the old Karakorum highway - is the emblem of 'Asha,' one of the seven Amesha Spenta ('Life-giving immortals') that sustain the good "thought world" and physical creations of Ahura Mazda.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Depictions of the judgment of the soul, its transition to the 'upper regions' and its welcome to the 'house of song' appear on Sogdian ossuaries, and Sogdian funerary monuments found near Xi'an.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– No

Notes: Such objects appear in other Sogdian contexts, but not on the document under consideration

↳ Humans

– No

Notes: See note above

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: This is not depicted through illustration, but through text. The text below the Ashem Vohu prayer (the third line onwards), refers to "the perfect righteous Zarathustra" coming to pay reverence to "the king of the gods, the...supreme god (Sogd. Adbag)" in "the sweet-smelling paradise in good thought" (Sims-Williams, "Sogdian Fragments", pp 46-47). Zarathustra addresses the divinity as "beneficent lawmaker, justly deciding judge" (ibid, p. 47)

↳ Human narratives

– No

Notes: Note that another fragment found in the Mogao Library cave (part now in the British Library collection, part in the Pelliot collection, Paris) which appears to have been written by the same scribe as the "Ashem Vohu" text, contains a story about Rostam, the mythical hero of Iranian lore. That story is not found in the Shahnameh, or depicted on any mural.

↳ Specify

–Specify: No specifications

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: There are aniconic images on some of the depictions of the Buddha found in the Library cave, but nothing similar relating to the 9th century Sogdian texts.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: In the tradition associated with the religion, the Gathas, or "songs" attributed to Zarathustra, which are in Old Avestan, were revealed by Ahura Mazda. Zarathustra was the first to recite them in the physical world.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

Notes: According to Young Avestan text, Ahura Mazda revealed the religion to the yazata ("being worthy of worship") Sraosha, who was the first to recite the Gathas in the thought world, and to teach the religion (Yt. 11.14).

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Within the religion, the earliest texts are thought to derive from "conversations" between Zarathustra and Ahura Mazda

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– Yes

Notes: Pahlavi texts present a cosmogonic scheme in which "knowledge of the religion" is transmitted through the spirit of the power of speech (mēnōg ī waxš nērōg) into the material world...

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: See various answers above

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: The religious texts were transmitted orally for centuries, during which time there was change in pronunciation. Once the texts were written down, there were changes in orthography, as evident from some of the differences between Iranian and Indian copies.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

Notes: Priests have provided normative interpretations of the texts, and of religious beliefs and practices. Since the mid-19th century, the study of Avestan and Middle Iranian (religious) texts have formed part of western academic curricula, and have been interpreted by scholars from those institutions.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: A trained male priesthood has been the group that has been historically responsible for transmitting the oral, then written texts. The Herbedestan, an Avestan text with Pahlavi gloss concerning the training of 'teaching priests,' indicates that anyone could go for priestly studies - men, women, children - provided they were capable.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

Notes: Information about training for the priesthood is only known from relatively recent sources. Nowadays, training can begin after initiation, which can be as early as seven.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– I don't know

Notes: The "Ashem Vohu" text does not refer to any priestly figure. One Sogdian Ancient Letter mentions a "bagnpat" or 'temple priest.' (The parallel term is also found in Parthian texts from Nisa). This usage indicates that the Sogdian Zoroastrian community in Dunhuang had its own place of worship by early 4th c. CE.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: The term "Avesta" is given to the oldest texts of the Zoroastrian religion, after the language in which they were composed, then written down. Much of the material is thought to have been lost.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: The "canon," such as it is, is closed, since it consists of texts belonging to an accepted line of transmission. The discovery of the Sogdian Zoroastrian version of the "Ashem Vohu" prayer, while not adding to the canon, provides breadth to the line of transmission through the eastern Iranian context.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Notes: The "canon" includes Pahlavi glosses and commentaries ("Zand") on the Avesta. These are recognized as part of the transmission of the religion, but there is ambivalence among Zoroastrians as to their religious authority (as also that of texts in Young Avestan).

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The "most sacred" part of the Avestan corpus is that composed in "Old Avestan," which includes the Gathas, five long poems ascribed to Zarathustra. Several ancient prayers are also ascribed to Zarathustra, including the Ashem Vohu prayer, preserved in this manuscript via Sogdian phonology.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The language of the Sogdian Ashem Vohu prayer differs from the Avestan version known from other (later) manuscripts, and also from standard Sogdian. It seems to present an Old Iranian form of the prayer (presumably preserved within a different tradition to the Avesta).

as we know it), as transcribed by someone who perhaps did not understand the ancient language.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: The Avestan script was specifically devised for writing the "Avestan" religious texts. The Sogdian form of the "Ashem Vohu" prayer is not in this script, nor a translation of the Avestan text as now known, but seems to preserve an Old Iranian form of the prayer independently of the form presented in the Sasanian-era Avestan script.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: The 9th century Pahlavi Zoroastrian books contain reference to the religion (den) being spoken in the obscure language of the Avesta (see, for instance, Dēnkard 5.31.12, 13)

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

Notes: Avestan, Middle Persian languages including Pahlavi and Sogdian, are taught at some secular universities.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Parts of the Yasna (liturgy), daily prayers, and other rituals may be read by Parsi Zoroastrian adherents in Gujarati transliteration, and by Iranian Zoroastrians in Persian transliteration. Translations into the vernacular are also used to support religious study of texts.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The Ashem Vohu prayer is recited several times at every ritual

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: The power of this and other ancient prayers (Av. "manthras") is thought to be activated through oral recitation.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

Notes: The power of this and other ancient prayers (Av. manthras) is thought to be activated through oral recitation.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: See above answer

↳ Is it read?

– No

Notes: Although the prayer is written down in this context, and was, presumably, intended to

be read along with the rest of the text, the particular phonological reproduction suggests that the scribe was familiar with hearing the prayer but not writing it. (It is suggested that he may not have been Zoroastrian). See note above regarding modern reading of the prayer in Gujarati or Persian transliteration.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
– Specify: Personal (such as when tying the kusti), and communal (during a festival).

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?
– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– Specify: Again, this will depend on the ritual. Personal prayer (particularly the untying/retying of the kusti) may take place several times a day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Yes

Notes: "Orthodoxy" is a sensitive term in this context. Iranian Zoroastrians who emigrate to India, and who seek to participate in Parsi religious and social activity, may be asked to affirm their religious adherence by performing the kusti ritual, which includes recitation of the Ashem Vohu prayer.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Yes

Notes: See note above.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– Yes

Notes: The Ashem Vohu forms part of individual prayer activity, as well as group prayer/worship.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: At an outer ritual (such as a seasonal gahanbar or family/community jashan), certain foods and liquid (milk, water, wine) will be consecrated (as chashni/myazd and zohr), to be shared by adherents after the recitation.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– No

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

Notes: The recitation of any mantra, such as the Ashem Vohu, is said to reverberate within both the "thought" world and the "material" world.

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

Notes: In so far as any perceived beneficent effects can be felt by humans...

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

Notes: In so far as all mantras, including the Ashem Vohu, are thought to enhance good and diminish evil.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The prayer is said by some adherents to calm the mind and bring peace. It may be recited when in a situation of physical or mental distress. In this respect it may be said to have a healing function.

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See notes above as to the perceived efficacy and "power" of the prayer.

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known on what material form(s) the original text was written. It was transmitted orally across a wide region, so one assumes existed in varied materialities.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– I don't know

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: There are no other known Sogdian versions of the prayer. This predates by 400 years extant Avestan versions of the prayer.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Ashem Vohu is contained within the Yasna, the Avestan liturgy, which includes a range of Avestan compositional forms and language. With regard to the Sogdian text in question, it seems that the same scribe wrote a copy of a story about the legendary Iranian hero Rustam, which was also in the Library Cave. This suggests there may have been other texts by the same scribe, both secular and sacred. Other Sogdian texts in the Library Cave are mostly Buddhist, with some Manichaean documents.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents qualify the authority of the Ashem Vohu prayer according to various perspectives: It is said to be one of the prayers recited by Zarathustra. In the Yasna liturgy, it is one of three prayers which introduce the Gathas, the "songs" ascribed to Zarathustra. It is ancient, and its authority is reinforced by being referenced in other Avestan texts around 200 times.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Unless missing segments of the Avesta are discovered...

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text emphasizes the centrality of the concept of "asha" ("area in this Sogdian form), meaning "order, right, truth."

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The prayer does not indicate any afterlife, but the passage beneath the prayer describes "the skillful supreme god...residing in the sweet-smelling paradise in good thought" (Nicholas Sims-Williams, 1976, pp. 46-47).

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Asha is one of the Amesha Spenta (Life-giving Immortals) active in promoting good/increase in both the thought and material worlds...

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Ahura Mazda is not mentioned in the Ashem Vohu prayer

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: See answer to above question about the presence of supernatural beings

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Asha is visible in the order manifest in the material world (such as the movement of the sun through the sky), and through the element of fire which is associated with Asha.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: See answer to question above

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: As with all yazatas, Asha is thought to have a positive, beneficent effect on invocers

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: The yazatas are on the side of those who adhere to Asha (the ashauuan); those

who adhere to the lie (dregwant/druhwant) are held to account

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Asha is referenced in many texts from the earliest period onward

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Ashem Vohu prayer invokes Asha, which can be translated as "order" "right" "truth". These qualities are both the focus of the prayer, and the aspiration of the reciter.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: no other categories of beings are present

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In so far as the prayer invokes Asha, it is assumed by the adherent that Asha is "present."

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In so far as the prayer invokes Asha, it is assumed by the adherent that Asha is "present" and the attendant qualities (of order, right, truth) therefore increased for the reciter(s).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: There is no specific eschatology present, but the various translations/interpretations of the prayer imply that following the orderly/right path brings "the best."

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

Notes: Ritual purity is not specified in the text, but it is often recited as part of ritual adherence, which would be performed in a state of "cleanness."

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates this virtue

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues. Pahlavi texts emphasise the importance of "payman" - balance, which would be coherent with this.

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not certain that the religion would consider these aspects "virtues." Although one of the other Amesha Spenta is Kshathra Vairya - "Chosen/Desirable Rule," indicating the beneficent use of power. It is assumed that the furthering of qualities associated with one of the Amesha Spenta would be coherent with the furthering of all the qualities associated with the other Amesha Spenta.

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Field doesn't know

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues. "Devotion" or "Right Mindedness" is the translation of another of the Amesha Spenta -

(Spenta) Armaiti. It is assumed that the furthering of qualities associated with one of the Amesha Spenta would be coherent with the furthering of all the qualities associated with the other Amesha Spenta.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the aspiration to further Asha as "order/right/truth" encapsulates these virtues.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Notes: Are these virtues?

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: When recited as part of ritual adherence, the adherent is generally in a state of "cleanness." The invocation of Asha, meaning "order," implies that orderliness would be a virtue advocated through the prayer - and effective in both the thought and material spheres.

↳ Other important virtues

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: During menses, women traditionally do not participate in ritual activity where a fire is present, but may still recite personal prayers.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The Ashem Vohu prayer seems to have been recited from the outset as part of individual praxis (such as when tying the kusti) in communal settings, and in the context of priestly ritual. Recitation in all instances requires commitment of time and focus.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The precept of following the path of Asha - that which is orderly, right, truth.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: It may be part of such ritual, but the ritual is not required for the recitation of the text.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: See response above.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Since the text had a long history of oral transmission before being written down, the social background of the groups that preserved the text changed considerably.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Through the millennia, the text of the Avesta seems to have been preserved - and commented upon - by a (male) hereditary priesthood, although the laity would have preserved the recitation of certain prayers. The appearance of the Ashem Vohu prayer on the Sogdian document found at Dunhuang indicates that the transmission of the texts was impacted by variant dialects.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Historically, the destruction of texts has been attributed to the Seleucids, who conquered the Ancient Persians in the late 4th century BCE, and to the incursion of the Arab Muslims from the mid-7th century onwards, who conquered the Sasanian Zoroastrians.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Interpretations of the text emphasize that the perpetuation of Asha will bring "the best" (happiness, things, etc.). This is not just an individual outcome, but on a cosmic level (which includes a societal impact).

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Avestan text Herbedestan, with its Pahlavi gloss and commentary (zand) indicates there was a formal place of religious learning, where the prayers and other texts of the religion would be studied. It is not known whether such a school existed in Sogdiana, or among the Sogdian communities in China. As of writing, there remains one school for priests in Mumbai. Modern Zoroastrians will learn the prayer from a parent, or a teacher (usually attached to a local community meeting place), or, in India, from a family panthaki.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The Sogdian preservation of the Ashem Vohu prayer is attached to a narrative that is religious in

content. The assumption is that it emerges from a context of familiarity with the religion (that is, of religious education)

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Although much of the larger textual tradition was transmitted orally, then interpreted, by a male priesthood, study of the texts were not confined to priests, or to men. See, for instance, earlier comment on the Herbedestan.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No